

Short Communication

Continuous fabrication of braided composite nanofibrous surgical yarns using advanced AC electrospinning and braiding technology

Divyabharathi Madheswaran^{a,b,**}, Manikandan Sivan^{b,*}, Sarka Hauzerova^b,
Eva Kuzelova Kostakova^b, Vera Jencova^b, Jan Valtera^c, Lubos Behalek^d, Jana Mullerova^b,
Nhung H.A. Nguyen^e, Lukas Capek^f, David Lukas^b

^a Department of Nonwovens and Nanofibrous Materials, Faculty of Textile Engineering, Technical University of Liberec, Liberec, Czech Republic

^b Department of Chemistry - Bioengineering, Faculty of Science, Humanities, and Education, Technical University of Liberec, Liberec, Czech Republic

^c Department of Textile Machine Design, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Liberec, Liberec, Czech Republic

^d Department of Engineering Technology, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Liberec, Liberec, Czech Republic

^e Centre for Nanomaterials, Advanced Technologies and Innovations, Technical University of Liberec, Liberec, Czech Republic

^f Department of Clinical Biomechanics, Regional Hospital Liberec, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

AC electrospinning

Braiding

Composite nanofibrous yarn

Surgical suture

ABSTRACT

Composite nanofibrous yarns (CNY), featuring a submicron electrospun sheath coated on a micro-scale core yarn have gained attention within the academic and industrial communities due to their unique structure. When braided, these CNYs hold great promise as next-generation surgical yarns. However, large-scale production of CNYs using conventional electrospinning techniques remains technologically challenging, and maintaining the integrity of the fibrous sheath during braiding presents further difficulties. Here, we propose a novel approach for continuously fabricating functional braided CNYs using collectorless alternating current (AC) electrospinning and braiding technology. Our approach utilized polycaprolactone-poly(lactic acid) (PCL-PLA) blends and PCL-PLA with chlorhexidine (CHX) or triclosan (TRC) electrospun fibers for the sheath layer, while PLA micro-yarns acted as the core layer. Morphological analyses confirmed the successful fabrication of braided CNYs. Additionally, infrared spectroscopy validated the presence of CHX or TRC in the resulting yarns. The resulting braided CNYs exhibited excellent breaking force (29 N) and thermal stability (270 °C). Cytotoxicity and antibacterial assessments demonstrated that CHX-loaded braided CNYs could serve as biocompatible antibacterial surgical sutures. The proposed method offers a versatile approach for producing various functional braided CNYs applicable in tissue engineering scaffolds, filters, wearable electronics, and sensors.

1. Introduction

In recent years, composite nanofibrous yarn (CNY), also known as core-sheath yarn, has emerged as a new type of suture material due to its ability to provide both essential functionality and mechanical strength. These yarns consist of a core-sheath structure; the sheath layer comprises nanofiber, while the core layer comprises classic yarn or micro-filaments. The core microfilaments provide the necessary mechanical supports to keep the incision closed and hold the wound's surrounding tissues together. Simultaneously, the fibrous sheath mimics the extracellular matrix, facilitating cellular activities. Additionally, it allows for

the loading of functional components such as antibacterial agents, anti-inflammatory substances, growth factors, and analgesics, thereby accelerating the wound healing process [1–6].

However, fabricating filament coated with electrospun nanofibrous (core-sheath) yarn using existing direct-current-based (DC) electrospinning technologies poses a technological challenge, requiring an electrically active or grounded collector to collect the charged electrospun fibers. Due to the repulsion caused by like charges, the polymer jet spreads out, resulting in fibers being deposited over a larger area. Therefore, depositing the electrospun fibers onto the electrically neutral core yarn to create CNY proves to be challenging. Furthermore, the

* Corresponding author.

** Corresponding author. Department of Nonwovens and Nanofibrous Materials, Faculty of Textile Engineering, Technical University of Liberec, Liberec, Czech Republic.

E-mail addresses: divyabharathi.madheswaran@tul.cz (D. Madheswaran), manikandan.sivan@tul.cz (M. Sivan).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coco.2024.101932>

Received 24 March 2024; Received in revised form 6 May 2024; Accepted 7 May 2024

Available online 8 May 2024

2452-2139/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

deposition of electrospun fibers is significantly influenced by the collector's geometry and position [5,7].

In contrast, when AC high-voltage is used, the spinning solution experiences simultaneously positive and negative charge polarities due to the rapid polarity changes. Additionally, AC potential builds a virtual collector a few centimeters away from the spinning electrode. Therefore, unlike DC, AC high-voltage creates a mechanically compact inter-connected fibrous structure, so-called fibrous plume [8–10]. This plume moves from the virtual collector aided by the surrounding electric wind and undergoes charge recombination, becoming electrically neutralized along its journey. Consequently, the electrospun fibers can be deposited onto an electrically-inactive stationary or moving substrate [11]. In our case, the fibrous plume is coated onto the microfilament core yarn. While CNYs exhibit combined functionality and acceptable mechanical properties, their structural integrity and the weak adhesive force between the core and nanofibrous sheath impede their utilization as mechanically robust functional surgical sutures.

Hence, this study proposes a method to prepare various functional braided CNYs for surgical suture applications. Initially, pristine and various functional CNYs were fabricated using free-surface collectorless AC electrospinning. Subsequently, they were braided using braiding technology to enhance the overall mechanical properties of these CNYs (Fig. 1). PCL and PLA blends were chosen due to their biocompatibility, biodegradability, and suitability for AC electrospinning [12]. CHX and TRC served as model antibacterial agents and are known for their efficiency against a wide range of microorganisms and biocompatibility. The chosen PLA microfilament yarn served as the core material, onto which the electrospun fibrous sheath was coated to create the desired core-nanofibrous sheath composite yarn. The study investigated the morphology, physicochemical characteristics, mechanical properties, thermal degradation, cytotoxicity, and antibacterial activity of the as-fabricated braided CNYs.

2. Materials and methods

Polycaprolactone (PCL) CAPA™ 6506 and polylactic acid (PLA, Ingeo™ biopolymer 4043D) were purchased from Perstorp and NatureWorks. Chlorhexidine (CHX), triclosan (TRC), dichloromethane (DCM), and sodium chloride (NaCl) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. PLA filament yarn with 250 dtex was provided by Sintex s.r.o. To prepare a blend PCL-PLA precursor solution, 5 wt% PCL, 2 wt% PLA, and 0.5 wt% NaCl were dissolved in DCM. To prepare a drug-loaded solution, 1 wt% CHX or TRC, 5 wt% PCL, and 2 wt% PLA were dissolved in DCM, so-called PCL-PLA-CHX or PCL-PLA-TRC. All solutions were stirred overnight at room temperature.

First, CNYs were fabricated by advanced collectorless AC electrospinning, and a detailed setup can be found in our previous articles

(Fig. 1) [6,11]. Briefly, the nanofibers were produced at 38 kV_{rms} (50 Hz sine waveform) using an ABB KGUG 36 high-voltage transformer and a Thalheimer-Trafowerke ESS 104 variable autotransformer. Due to the high voltage polarity changes, the compact fibrous plume was created, which was further moved upright and subsequently coated on axially rotating and ballooning PLA core yarn. The velocity of the core yarn was maintained at 30 m/min. The electrospun fiber-coated yarn passed through a drying zone (length 2.2 m) and afterward wound up on the bobbins. The processing parameters are given in the supporting information (Table S1).

Second, the CNYs were braided using an EY-RA-8-4 (110 II) braiding machine with customized yarn carriers (Fig. 1). The CNYs were mounted on each carrier of the braiding machine (8 carriers + 1 central carrier) to create braided CNY. The production rate of the braided CNYs was 0.25 m/min. Characterization methods, such as the morphological, physicochemical, thermal, and mechanical properties as well as antibacterial and cytocompatibility assessment of as-fabricated yarns, are available in the supplementary file.

3. Result and discussion

3.1. Fabrication of braided composite nanofibrous yarn

The pristine PCL-PLA, PCL-PLA-CHX, and PCL-PLA-TRC solutions were employed to fabricate the CNYs. The PCL-PLA solution initially failed to produce a steady fibrous plume due to poor AC spinnability. However, the addition of 0.5 wt% NaCl significantly improved its AC spinnability, resulting in the formation of a steady fibrous plume. Consequently, the PCL-PLA fibrous plume was coated onto the running PLA core yarn (30 m/min), thereby forming the desired core (PLA) - sheath (PCL-PLA) CNY. Comparatively, PCL-PLA-TRC exhibited a denser fibrous plume, followed by PCL-PLA-CHX and pristine PCL-PLA solutions. This observation indicates that drug-loaded solutions exhibited better AC spinnability without the addition of NaCl.

The morphology of various braided CNYs and PLA core yarn was examined by SEM and is depicted in Fig. 2a–h. The SEM images illustrate the uniform electrospun deposition on the PLA core yarn. For each sample, 9 CNYs were utilized to create braided CNY. Throughout the braiding process, the maximum tension in the CNY was maintained at ~32 cN, facilitated by the custom-built yarn carrier, ensuring a smooth and efficient braiding process. SEM images of various braided CNYs indicate that the nanofibrous sheath layer remained undamaged and did not peel off from the CNY during or after braiding. Higher-resolution SEM images revealed clusters of beads on the string-like fibrous structure for PLA/PCL-PLA-TRC. Conversely, spindles and beads were observed on the fibrous surfaces of PLA/PCL-PLA and PLA/PCL-PLA-CHX.

Fig. 1. The braided CNY preparation process using AC electrospinning and braiding technology.

Fig. 2. SEM images of braided PLA core yarn (a and b) and various braided CNYs at different magnifications (c–h), the linear density of as-braided yarns (i), the theoretical linear density of the fibrous sheath layer (j), and the braiding angle and number of pitches/cm of as-fabricated yarns (k).

The gravimetric method was used to analyze as-fabricated yarn's linear density and theoretical linear density of electrospun fibrous sheath (Fig. 2i and j). The linear density of braided PLA core filament yarn is 2371 dtex. The pristine PLA/PCL-PLA braided CNY was 2595 dtex, in which 224 dtex (8.4 %) is covered by the nanofibrous envelope,

and the remaining 2371 dtex (91.6 %) is core yarn. For the CHX and TRC loaded braided yarns, the linear density was 2670 dtex and 3070 dtex, in which 299 dtex (11.2 %) and 699 dtex (22.8 %) of nanofibers are covered on the core yarn 2371 (88.8 %) dtex and 2371 (77.2 %) dtex, respectively. The observed difference in the linear density of the

Fig. 3. (a) FT-IR spectra, (b) TGA thermogram, (c) DTG thermogram, (d) force-extension curve, (e) maximum breaking force, and (f) extension of braided CNYs.

electrospun fibrous sheath among the as-fabricated yarns is attributed to the spinnability of the spinning solutions, which affects electrospun fiber productivity.

The higher diameter, braiding angle, and number of pitches/cm (Fig. 2k) observed in the braided PLA/PCL-PLA-TRC yarn results from its higher linear density. Compared to the braided core yarn, the slight reduction in diameter observed in the braided pristine and CHX-loaded yarn is attributed to the nanofiber coating process and additional twisting during composite yarn fabrication, which tightened the CNY structure. Conversely, the multistranded structure and fraying of the PLA core yarn resulted in a larger diameter. Variations in braiding tension and compression also influence the diameter of the as-fabricated braided yarn, with the core yarn experiencing less compression during braiding. Additionally, the braiding angle and the number of pitches/cm impact the diameter by affecting yarn distribution and compression during the braiding process.

3.2. The physicochemical, thermal, and mechanical properties of as-fabricated yarns

The functional group analysis of various braided yarns was examined by FTIR (Fig. 3a). For PLA, peaks at 2997 and 2954 cm^{-1} corresponded to asymmetric and symmetric CH stretching vibrations, respectively. Additionally, bands at 1748, 1453, 1383, 1358, 1128, and 1043 cm^{-1} were attributed to C=O stretching, CH_3 bending, CH-asymmetric, symmetric deformation, C–O stretching, and OH bending, respectively. Concerning PCL, peaks at 2919 and 2851 cm^{-1} were assigned to asymmetric and symmetric CH_2 stretching, while bands at 1722, 1294, 1238, and 1180 cm^{-1} were associated with C=O stretching, C–O & C–C stretching in the crystalline phase, and C–O asymmetric and symmetric stretching, respectively [13]. As expected, all the characteristic peaks of PLA and PCL were recognized in PLA/PCL-PLA braided CNY with changes in the intensity and wavenumber of the spectra [14]. CHX exhibited peaks at 1632 cm^{-1} (C=N–H stretching) and 1531/1493 cm^{-1} (aromatic C=C stretching) [15], while TRC showed characteristic peaks at 1597, 1508, and 1472 cm^{-1} , indicating C=C stretching. Moreover, the presence of C–Cl stretching was confirmed by the peak at 791 cm^{-1} [16]. The FTIR spectra of braided CNYs confirmed the presence of characteristic peaks from both PLA and PCL. In drug-loaded braided CNYs, the FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of characteristic peaks corresponding to both the polymers and the drugs (CHX or TRC). In the case of PLA/PCL-PLA-TRC, the intensity of the C=O peak related to PCL was observed to be higher than that of PLA. This observation coincided with the respective linear densities, with PCL constituting 436.9 dtex and PLA comprising 174.8 dtex of the electrospun fibrous sheath (Fig. 2j).

The thermal stability was determined using thermogravimetric analysis, and the corresponding thermograms are depicted in (Fig. 3b and c). For better visualization of the degradation process, the first derivative of the thermogram (DTG) is also presented in Fig. 3c. All fabricated samples showed thermal stability up to 270 °C. The braided PLA core yarn's maximum degradation temperature (T_{max}) was observed at 344 °C with a single-step degradation. In comparison, PLA/PCL-PLA, PLA/PCL-PLA-CHX, and PLA/PCL-PLA-TRC exhibited two-step degradation. The first (T_{max1}) and second (T_{max2}) degradation temperatures of PLA/PCL-PLA were located at 332 and 361 °C, corresponding to PLA and PCL, respectively [14]. For PLA/PCL-PLA-CHX and PLA/PCL-PLA-TRC, T_{max1} was observed at 334 and 336 °C (corresponding to PLA). Meanwhile, T_{max2} was observed at 368 and 376 °C (related to PCL), respectively. The variations in T_{max1} and T_{max2} of pristine and drug-loaded samples clearly indicate the incorporation of CHX or TRC in the resultant braided yarns. Moreover, from Fig. 2j and 3b or 3c, it is evident that the T_{max2} peak intensity corresponding to PCL degradation increased as the linear density of the fibrous envelope increased (from 224 to 299 and 699 dtex). This is due to a 2.5 times higher amount of PCL (5 wt%) than PLA (2 wt%) in the fibrous envelope

(Fig. 2j). TGA analysis further confirmed the presence of polymers and drugs in the braided CNYs.

The mechanical properties of the braided CNYs were evaluated in terms of maximum breaking force and extension (Fig. 3d–f). Comparing the PLA braided core yarn with the braided CNYs revealed no significant difference in maximum breaking force ($p > 0.05$). This indicates that the PLA core yarn consistently maintains maximum breaking force, regardless of the linear density of its fibrous sheath layer, braiding angle, and number of pitches/cm. However, the PLA/PCL-PLA-TRC exhibited significantly greater extension than the other yarns ($p < 0.05$). This enhanced extension is likely influenced by the higher braiding angle and pitches per centimeter observed in the PLA/PCL-PLA-TRC, resulting from the increased linear density of its nanofibrous sheath layer. Additionally, the higher PCL content in the fibrous sheath contributes to its greater elasticity, as PCL inherently possesses greater elasticity. As previously mentioned, in terms of mechanical properties, the PLA microfilament core layer contributes to the overall tensile breaking force while the electrospun sheath, braiding angle and number of pitches/cm contribute to the extension, particularly in the case of PLA/PCL-PLA-TRC.

3.3. Antibacterial efficiency and cytocompatibility of as-fabricated yarns

The antibacterial activity of as-fabricated materials was analyzed by agar diffusion test, and results are presented in Fig. 4a. Both Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacterial strains were selected, as these strains commonly contribute to healthcare-associated infections. CHX or TRC diffuses from the drug-loaded samples and subsequently inhibits bacterial growth, resulting in a zone of inhibition. A clear inhibition zone of 2.25 ± 0.8 mm and 2.3 ± 0.5 mm can be observed on PLA/PCL-PLA-CHX for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, respectively. In the case of PLA/PCL-PLA-TRC, 9.6 ± 0.8 mm and 7.5 ± 1.7 mm were observed for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, respectively. The higher inhibition zone of TRC-loaded yarn could be attributed to a higher amount of TRC (524 μg) than CHX (224 μg) in the braided yarn (length: 6 cm) used (Fig. S1). In contrast, as expected, bacterial growth (no inhibition zone) can be seen on pristine PLA/PCL-PLA, indicating that this braided yarn does not have antibacterial activity.

The antibacterial effect of drug-loaded materials must be balanced with the safety of eukaryotic cells, as they also require antibacterial protection. Therefore, the cytocompatibility of as-fabricated samples was examined by MTT assay with respect to their length (Fig. 4b). The drug-free PLA/PCL-PLA showed higher cell viability than the drug-loaded samples, showing good biocompatibility. The increased metabolic activity in the 2 cm PLA/PCL-PLA yarn, compared to the 4 and 6 cm lengths, may be due to NaCl additive within the PCL-PLA nanofibrous sheath, known for its osmotic effect [17]. Approximately 30 μg of NaCl could have leached from the 2 cm yarn into the culture media, triggering osmotic pressure and resulting in higher metabolic activity than the longer lengths (Fig. 4b and S2). PLA/PCL-PLA yarns of 4 and 6 cm lengths showed a slight reduction in metabolic activity, attributed to slightly higher NaCl leaching (60 and 90 μg , respectively). With the exception of the 6 cm length PLA/PCL-PLA-CHX, the 2 and 4 cm lengths exhibited cytocompatibility. In contrast, PLA/PCL-PLA-TRC showed cytotoxicity regardless of their lengths, as their cell viability was less than 70%. As the length of the drug-loaded sample increased, a significantly higher amount of drug could have eluted into the cell media, consequently leading to decreased cell viability (Fig. 4b and S2). It was reported that cell viability was oppositely proportional to an above-certain CHX or TRC threshold concentration [18,19].

However, strategies such as braiding a combination of pristine and drug-loaded CNYs can enhance the biocompatibility of drug-loaded samples. By positioning the drug-loaded CNY at the core of the braided yarn structure and surrounding it with pristine CNYs, a protective barrier is created, limiting direct contact between the drug and surrounding tissues and thus enhancing biocompatibility. These

Fig. 4. (a) Antibacterial efficiency of braided CNYs against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and (b) cell viability as a function of various lengths of braided CNYs.

strategies offer promising avenues for balancing antibacterial efficacy and biocompatibility in drug-loaded braided yarns, rendering them suitable for various surgical applications.

4. Conclusion

Composite yarns, characterized by a submicron electrospun sheath coated on micro-scale core yarn, have emerged as promising materials for next-generation sutures. However, their practical application has been impeded by technological challenges in fabrication and inadequate mechanical strength. Therefore, this study presents a novel approach to produce mechanically robust, functional braided CNY using advanced AC electrospinning and braiding technology. SEM analysis confirmed the successful fabrication of both pristine and antibacterial braided CNYs. Validation of CHX or TRC presence in the as-fabricated yarns was achieved through FT-IR analysis. Notably, resulting yarns exhibited a tensile breaking force of 29 N and demonstrated thermal stability up to 270 °C. Moreover, cytotoxicity and antibacterial properties assessments revealed that the PLA/PCL-PLA-CHX is biocompatible and possesses suitable antibacterial efficacy for surgical suture applications. Further exploration of the balanced antibacterial effects and cytocompatibility of braided yarns will be pursued using the braiding technology.

This research presents promising pathways for developing advanced surgical sutures with enhanced strength and antimicrobial capabilities. Such advancements hold the potential to significantly improve patient health and reduce the risk of post-surgical infections.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Divyabharathi Madheswaran: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Manikandan Sivan:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sarka Hauzerova:** Methodology, Data curation. **Eva Kuzelova Kostakova:** Writing – review & editing. **Vera Jencova:** Writing – review & editing. **Jan Valtera:** Resources. **Lubos Behalek:** Formal analysis. **Jana Mullerova:** Formal analysis. **Nhung H.A. Nguyen:** Formal analysis. **Lukas Capek:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **David Lukas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgment

This research was supported by the “Centre of Excellence in Regenerative Medicine” project, registration number CZ.02.01.01/00/22.008/0004562 of the European Union Programme entitled Johannes Amos Comenius in the call “Excellent Research”, Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic, Technical University of Liberec (SGS-2021-4007), and cluster Nanoprogress z.s.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coco.2024.101932>.

References

- [1] S. Wu, T. Dong, Y. Li, M. Sun, Y. Qi, J. Liu, M.A. Kuss, S. Chen, B. Duan, State-of-the-art review of advanced electrospun nanofiber yarn-based textiles for biomedical applications, *Appl. Mater. Today* 27 (2022) 101473, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2022.101473>.
- [2] M. Zhang, L. Chu, J. Chen, F. Qi, X. Li, X. Chen, D.-G. Yu, Asymmetric wettability fibrous membranes: preparation and biologic applications, *Compos. Part B Eng.* 269 (2024) 111095, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.111095>.
- [3] H. Liu, H. Wang, X. Lu, V. Murugadoss, M. Huang, H. Yang, F. Wan, D.-G. Yu, Z. Guo, Electrospun structural nanohybrids combining three composites for fast helicide delivery, *Adv. Compos. Hybrid Mater.* 5 (2022) 1017–1029, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42114-022-00478-3>.
- [4] H. Zheng, X. Li, L. Liu, C. Bai, B. Liu, H. Liao, M. Yan, F. Liu, P. Han, H. Zhang, J. He, Preparation of nanofiber core-spun yarn based on cellulose nanowhiskers/quaternary ammonium salts nanocomposites for efficient and durable antibacterial textiles, *Compos. Commun.* 36 (2022) 101388, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coco.2022.101388>.
- [5] Y. Wang, Z. Wang, H. Fu, H. Li, J. Tan, W. Yang, Preparation and functional applications of electrospun yarns, in: *Funct. Nanofibers*, Elsevier, 2023, pp. 109–133, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-99461-3.00021-2>.
- [6] D. Madheswaran, M. Sivan, J. Valtera, E.K. Kostakova, T. Egghe, M. Asadian, V. Novotny, N.H.A. Nguyen, A. Sevcu, R. Morent, N. De Geyter, D. Lukas, Composite yarns with antibacterial nanofibrous sheaths produced by collectorless alternating-current electrospinning for suture applications, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 139 (2022) 51851, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.51851>.
- [7] F. Mokhtari, M. Salehi, F. Zamani, F. Hajiani, F. Zeighami, M. Latifi, Advances in electrospinning: the production and application of nanofibres and nanofibrous structures, *Textil. Prog.* 48 (2016) 119–219, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405167.2016.1201934>.
- [8] M. Sivan, D. Madheswaran, J. Valtera, E.K. Kostakova, D. Lukas, Alternating current electrospinning: the impacts of various high-voltage signal shapes and frequencies on the spinnability and productivity of polycaprolactone nanofibers, *Mater. Des.* 213 (2022) 110308, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2021.110308>.
- [9] M. Sivan, D. Madheswaran, S. Hauzerova, V. Novotny, V. Hedvicakova, V. Jencova, E.K. Kostakova, M. Schindler, D. Lukas, AC electrospinning: impact of high voltage and solvent on the electrospinnability and productivity of polycaprolactone electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds, *Mater. Today Chem.* 26 (2022) 101025, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtchem.2022.101025>.

- [10] T. Kalous, P. Holec, R. Jirkovec, O. Batka, P. Zabka, P. Pokorny, P. Stepanova, J. Chvojka, The effect of frequency change on the alternating current electrospinning of polyamide 6 and its productivity, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 11 (2023) 109543, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.109543>.
- [11] J. Valtera, T. Kalous, P. Pokorny, O. Batka, M. Bilek, J. Chvojka, P. Mikes, E. K. Kostakova, P. Zabka, J. Ornstova, J. Beran, A. Stanishevsky, D. Lukas, Fabrication of dual-functional composite yarns with a nanofibrous envelope using high throughput AC needleless and collectorless electrospinning, *Sci. Rep.* 9 (2019) 1801, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-38557-z>.
- [12] K. Havlickova, E. Kuzelova Kostakova, M. Lisnenko, S. Hauzerova, M. Stuchlik, S. Vrchovicka, L. Vistejnova, J. Molacek, D. Lukas, R. Prochazkova, J. Horakova, S. Jakubkova, B. Heczakova, V. Jencova, The impacts of the sterilization method and the electrospinning conditions of nanofibrous biodegradable layers on their degradation and hemocompatibility behavior, *Polymers* 16 (2024) 1029, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16081029>.
- [13] M. Sivan, D. Madheswaran, M. Asadian, P. Cools, M. Thukkaram, P. Van Der Voort, R. Morent, N. De Geyter, D. Lukas, Plasma treatment effects on bulk properties of polycaprolactone nanofibrous mats fabricated by uncommon AC electrospinning: a comparative study, *Surf. Coating. Technol.* 399 (2020) 126203, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2020.126203>.
- [14] P. Prajontat, C. Sriprachuabwong, R. Wongkanya, D. Dechtrirat, J. Sudchanham, N. Srisamran, W. Sangthong, P. Chuysinuan, A. Tuantranont, S. Hannongbua, N. Chattham, Moisture-resistant electrospun polymer membranes for efficient and stable fully printable perovskite solar cells prepared in humid air, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 11 (2019) 27677–27685, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.9b05032>.
- [15] J.G. Fernandes, D.M. Correia, G. Botelho, J. Padrão, F. Dourado, C. Ribeiro, S. Lanceros-Méndez, V. Sencadas, PHB-PEO electrospun fiber membranes containing chlorhexidine for drug delivery applications, *Polym. Test.* 34 (2014) 64–71, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2013.12.007>.
- [16] M. Orhan, Triclosan applications for biocidal functionalization of polyester and cotton surfaces, *J. Eng. Fabr.* 15 (2020) 155892502094010, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558925020940104>.
- [17] E. Stubblefield, G.C. Mueller, Effects of sodium chloride concentration on growth, biochemical composition, and metabolism of HeLa cells, *Cancer Res.* 20 (1960) 1646–1655.
- [18] J. Song, S.J.A. Remmers, J. Shao, E. Kolwijck, X.F. Walboomers, J.A. Jansen, S.C. G. Leeuwenburgh, F. Yang, Antibacterial effects of electrospun chitosan/poly (ethylene oxide) nanofibrous membranes loaded with chlorhexidine and silver, *Nanomed. Nanotechnol. Biol. Med.* 12 (2016) 1357–1364, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nano.2016.02.005>.
- [19] L.J. del Valle, R. Camps, A. Díaz, L. Franco, A. Rodríguez-Galán, J. Puiggali, Electrospinning of polylactide and polycaprolactone mixtures for preparation of materials with tunable drug release properties, *J. Polym. Res.* 18 (2011) 1903–1917, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10965-011-9597-3>.